

Distributive Justice And Organizational Commitment In Oil And Gas Company In Delta State, Nigeria

Agari Evi Prosper

**Department of Business Administration,
Faculty Of Management Sciences,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This work investigated the effect of distributive justice and organizational commitment in oil and Gas Company in Delta State, Nigeria. The study aim to examine the effect of equity in pay level on employee continuance commitment; equal recognition justice on affective commitment and gas the effect of rewards distributive justice on normative commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria . Relevant theoretical and empirical literature were examined. The study was anchored on Equity Theory. Descriptive survey design was adopted. The study was carried out in Delta State,, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 600 employees of two oil and gas company in Delta State The sample size consist of the entire population (600). The instrument used for the study was questionnaire. Face and content validity was adopted while, test re-test and Cronbach Alpha method were carried out to achieve reliability of the instrument. Simple percentage analysis was employed to answer the research questions and Simple Regression analysis was used in testing the hypothesis. Results showed that equity in pay level distributive justice has a significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies; equal recognition justice has a significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies and rewards distributive justice has a significant positive effect on normative commitment in oil and gas firms in Delta State,, Nigeria. The study concluded that distributive justice had a significant positive effect on employee commitment oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria. The study recommended that management oil and gas firms should adopt equity in pay level distributive justice to enhance employee commitment and transparent structure that ensures equitable compensation for employees based on their qualifications, experience, and responsibilities eliminate perceptions of unfairness and promote employee commitment within organization.

Keyword: Equity in Pay Level Distributive Justice, Equal Recognition Justice, Rewards Distributive Justice and Employee Commitment

INTRODUCTION

The company's success in achieving its goals cannot be separated from the commitment of employees or human resources. According to Meyer & Smith, (2000) the successful use of human resources can help grow employee commitment. Likewise for employees. Employee commitment is the strength of an individual's identification and involvement in a particular organization. Commitment is the bond employees experience with their organization. Broadly speaking, employees who are committed to their organization, feel that they fit in and, feel they understand the goals and objectives of the organization. The added value of such employees is that they tend to be more determined in their work, show relatively high productivity and are more proactive in offering in offering their support. A very important factor in

achieving organizational goals is distributive justice. Gibson et al (2009) revealed that distributive justice shows the appropriate distribution of rights and obligations within an organization. One form of distributive justice is justice in obtaining compensation in the form of rewards, incentives, bonuses or allowances. The better the distribution of justice felt by an employee at work will encourage job satisfaction to appear.

Distributive justice is the perception of the extent to which rewards are allocated fairly by the organization. Examples of distributive justice are salaries, recognition, bonuses, rewards, and so on. The concept of distributive justice corresponds to the perception of fairness about the amount of compensation received by employees or workers. In the repertoire of organizational justice theory, distributive justice is the first concept to emerge. Initiated the theory of distributive justice by calling this theory the equity theory, which is closely related to results or rewards. In general, the perception of distributive justice is legitimized by comparing what one person receives with that received by another party in the same or equivalent timeline and structure (Greenberg 2017). Brown, (2016) states that distributive justice occurs when the more powerful partners are aware that they have some kind of obligation regarding the other partner's benefits and can be measured by identifying how the benefits and burdens are divided between the two parties. Although many social situations can be understood in terms of exchange, this framework is unable to include a concentration on justice. [12], made a general distinction about benefits between parties, namely two-way transfer of resource values and one-way distribution of resources through recipient or allocation cycle categories. Allocation occurs when the allocator distributes value in the form of gifts, resources, rights, obligations, etc. to the recipients of the allocated allocations that have been prepared. It doesn't matter whether the recipients are directly involved with each other. The tendency of change towards distributive justice is often found in various organizations. The lack of employee contribution to the organization in which they work, is one of the tendencies to decrease distributive justice to employees. Ineffective and inefficient task completion times, high levels of errors in completing work, or other weaknesses are only one of the trends of decreasing employee distributive justice. Conditions like this should be a signal for the organization to take earlier steps to repeat it. Distributive justice certainly has a goal to make the work that has been given can be carried out as well as possible. The distributive dimension of organizational justice is a very important factor for any types of organization for their effective functioning. Employees with high degree of distributive justice perception will show dedication to the development of organizations, pay attention on self-development, and pay attention to their work. Such situation may enhance or boost the employees to put more effort for organizational effectiveness. When employees perceive that they are treated based on fair procedures in determining outcome, they may tend to show better performance. Employees may feel they are rewarded fairly based on their actual commitment.

Objectives of the Study

The overall objective of the study is to examine the effect of organizational justice on employee commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives are to

1. Examine the influence of equity in pay level on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South Nigeria
2. Determine the effect of equal recognition distributive justice on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria
3. Access the effect of rewards distributive justice on normative commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research question were formulate in line with the objectives of the study

1. To what degree does equity in pay level distributive justice affect employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South Nigeria?
2. To what level does equal recognition distributive justice on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria?

3. How does rewards distributive justice affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study to give direction to the study at 0.5 level of significance

Ho₁: Equity in pay level distributive justice has no significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Ho₂: Equal recognition distributive justice has no significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Ho₃: Rewards distributive justice has no significant effect on affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Distributive Justice

Distributive justice is the perception of the extent to which rewards are allocated fairly by the organization. Examples of distributive justice are salaries, recognition, bonuses, rewards, and so on. The concept of distributive justice corresponds to the perception of fairness about the amount of compensation received by employees or workers. In the repertoire of organizational justice theory, distributive justice is the first concept to emerge. Initiated the theory of distributive justice by calling this theory the equity theory, which is closely related to results or rewards. In general, the perception of distributive justice is legitimized by comparing what one person receives with that received by another party in the same or equivalent timeline and structure. Gibson et al (2009) revealed that distributive justice shows the appropriate distribution of rights and obligations within an organization. One form of distributive justice is justice in obtaining compensation in the form of rewards, incentives, bonuses or allowances. Distributive justice refers to the perception of an employee regarding the suitability and fairness of what he or she receives in the organization (Fuchs & Edwards, 2012). It is concerned with an employee perception of fair treatment with respect to outcomes allocation after comparing his or her input-outcome ratio with those of his or her colleagues (Rahman et al, 2016). This is why Cropanzano et al (2007) defined distributive justice as the perceived degree of fairness in the rewards and benefits received by an employee in an organization. Distributive justice occurs when there is a congruency of actual and expected outcomes (Jawad et al, 2012). Distributive justice perception refers to individuals' perceived fairness of decision outcomes or perceived equity in relation to relevant others as propounded by (Greenberg, 2017). Distributive justice perception reflects an individual's interpretation as to whether their employment outcomes are fair, appropriate and ethical (Yucel, 2018). An employment outcome is usually thought of as some decision that has been rendered regarding the employee. Individuals may perceive their employment outcomes (salary, salary increment, promotion, benefits,) as fair or unfair. They compare their outcomes with those of others. As a result of their comparison they may believe that they are treated fairly or unfairly. This belief influences their attitude towards the organization (Gurbuz & Mert, 2019).

One of the key outcomes of distributive justice is employee commitment towards the organization (Akanbi & Ofoegbu (2018). Employees expect certain outcomes based on their inputs (skills, experience, ability, time and efforts) to ensure that their organization achieve its set goals. The outcomes include salary, pay rise, promotion, fringe benefits (bonuses and allowances), incentives and recognition (Hassan, 2002). If the allocation decisions are perceived to be fair, the employee will exhibit good work behaviours such as organizational citizenship behaviour and job commitment, but where the employee perceives the outcomes or allocation decisions to be unfair and unjust, he or she is likely to react negatively by increasing absenteeism, late coming, non-commitment to work and increased tendency to leave the organization (Hassan, 2002). Fuchs and Edwards (2012) agreed with Hassans point of view when they stated that an employee is less likely to perform, produce and remain committed to the organization if he or she perceives unfair compensation. The behavioural implication of distributive justice calls for the

need for decision makers to take the issue of distributive justice more serious than ever. This is because employees will always compare their outcomes with those of their colleagues (referents within the organization) and make judgment on the equitableness of the outcomes. If an employee perceives outcome he or she receives to be similar to those of the referents (colleagues), he or she will conclude that there is distributive justice in the organization. However, if the employee perceives outcomes he or she receives to differ with those of the referents (colleagues) i.e. under-compensation or over-compensation, he or she can say that there is distributive injustice in the organization (Hassan, 2002). In the case of under-compensation, the employee will retaliate, demonstrates a negative behaviour and generates tension in the form of anger or resentment. However, in the case where the employee is overcompensated, he or she will develop a feeling of guilt (Hassan, 2002). If there is distributive injustice, managers need to take urgent steps to correct the discrepancy. This requires a cognitive action to change the perceived outcomes to ensure that there is equality in the distribution of outcomes. The action taken by management may result in behavioural change in the form of increase or decrease in inputs of the concerned worker. Meanwhile, Cropanzano et al (2007) spelt out three allocation rules that need to be applied in order to appropriately establish distributive justice in modern organizations. First, management needs to ensure that there is equality in the distribution of outcomes to each worker in the same level. Secondly, establish equity in outcomes allocation to each worker in accordance with their contributions, and thirdly, address the specific needs of each worker in accordance with the most urgency.

This is the notion of fair distribution. It is concerned with the fair allocation of resources among diverse members of the organization. According to the theory of relative deprivation, a sense of individuals come to believe that their outcome is not in balance with the outcomes received by people like them in similar situations. When people have a sense that they are at an unfair disadvantage relative to others, or that they have not received their fair share may wish to challenge the system that has given rise to this state of affairs. This is likely to happen if a person or groups' fundamental needs are not being met. According to Hegtvedt, (2018), individuals perceive a sense of justice when the amount of reward received corresponds to the amount regarded as just based on distributive justice principles.

Equity in Pay Level: Equity in pay level simply means that workers in the same grade level should be given equal pay to ensure that there is distributive justice in the organization. Pay refers to the amount of money which an employee receives from his or her employer for a job done (George et al, 2016). It is the compensation or financial reward which an employee get from his or her employer for work done (Kazaz et al, 2008). Pay is important to both employer and employee. To employers, pay enables them to improve their competitiveness in the labour market and attract more talented and skilled persons to their organization (Negash et al, 2014). Employers also use pay to place value on individual employees based on their skills, knowledge, experience and contribution to the organization (Mabaso & Dlamini, 2017). Pay is also important to employees because it has a great influence on employees' morale, retention and turnover rate (Quartey & Attiogbe, 2013). It also affect employees' attitude to work as well as their level of commitment to the organization (Jean et al, 2017). To employees, a good pay enables them to meets their needs and improve their standard of living (Feraro-Banta & Al-Shaikh, 2017). Masca (2016) stated that employees use pay to evaluate their organization's financial strength and the value that they placed on the organization. Employees also use pay to assess the value which their organization placed on them (Osibanjo et al, 2014). Pay differentiates employees' social status in the society. In Nigeria, many employees switch from one organization to another in search for better pay. A survey conducted by Adewale (2014) revealed that seven out of every ten Nigerian employees are interested in changing their job and the main reason cited by these employees for such move is due to poor pay structure in their present job. However, Idemobi (2011) opined that an average employee is only willing to remain with his or her current organization if the pay he or she receives commensurate with his or her contribution (input). He further stated that poor pay is the major reason why most employees in Nigeria move from one organization to another. They added that poor pay and inequality in pay structure have been the major factors that make many Nigerians to move to other cities and countries in search for a well aid job. Equity in pay covers wages, salaries as well as overtime pay. According to Mabaso and Dlamini (2017), wages

refer to the amount of money paid to workers on an hourly, daily or weekly basis. Larbi (2014) stated that workers who are paid on hourly, daily or weekly basis are known as wage earners. An employee's wage rate is calculated based on the unit of output produced per day, hour or week (Njoroge & Kwasira, 2015). Wages decisions are important decisions which every organization must make. Employers must decide the wage level and wage structure. However, the wage structure of an organization is affected by a number of factors which include: the nature of job to be performed, compensation policy of the organization, the ability of the organization to pay, the condition of the labour market, the cost of living in the country, collective bargaining, government regulations, level of productivity, quality of the workforce, and technological change (Masea, 2016). Employers must consider these factors when fixing their wage structure for workers. An organization can decide to pay a higher wage to motivate and retain its productive and talented workforce. Kuster and Canales (2011) stated that the advantage of paying a higher wages is not only to motivate and retain the most productive and skilled workforce but also to attract top talents to the organization. Although paying a higher wages increases the operational costs of the organization, it also has the benefits of boosting the capacity of the organization to compete for quality labour in the labour market (Jean et al, 2017). However, the decision of an organization to pay lower wages makes it difficult for the organization to compete for top quality labour in the labour market. Although, an organization that pay lower wages may save money from the cost of labour but it stands the risk of losing productive and valuable labour to its competitors (Negash et al, 2014).

Equal Promotion Opportunity: Equal promotion opportunity simply means that workers in the same grade level should be given equal promotion opportunity irrespective of their tribe, race, religious affiliation and ethnic nationality to ensure that there is distributive justice in the organization. Promotion is the advancement of an employee from one job position to another job position that has a higher salary range, a higher job title and often more and higher level job responsibilities (Neil, 2000). Ali and Ahmad (2017) defined promotion as the advancement of an employee from one rank or position to the next one in the hierarchy system. It involves climbing the corporate ladder or when an individual move from one designation to a higher one (Ali & Ahmad, 2017). The purpose of promotion in any business organization is to motivate the workers towards increasing their productivity. Certain job positions with excellent promotion prospects have been the objects of hot pursuits and desires of workers in any business organization. Sometimes a promotion results in an employee taking on responsibility or managing or overseeing the work of other employees. Decision making authority tends to rise with a promotion as well. Visually, a promotion moves an employee's job up one level on an organizational chart (Heathfield, 2011). Promotion is seen as a way of recognition for employees who make significant and effective work contributions. Promotion is desirable by employees because it comes with higher pay, authority, responsibility and the ability to influence broader organizational decision making (Heathfield, 2011). Promotion raises the status of the employee who receives a promotion which is a visible sign of esteem from the employer (Heathfield, 2011). It comes with a higher compensation, internal and external status, greater autonomy, interesting challenges and the like. Other things attached to the promotion of workers include incentives, increased allowances, accommodation, drivers, messengers and company cars. For some employees the key to job continuity is promotion. When the promotion expectation is not met there is this tendency to leave the organization for a better job offer. Most of employees when promoted feel that their status has improved which gives them power and even additional paid. The reason why employee wants promotion vary from person to person. Some want promotion because they are bored with their current job and feel like that their expertise are not utilize properly, some want to be promoted because they may not be having good relationship with their supervisor or simply they want to have a higher status job. All these factors lead to motivation which enhance employee's performance and boost organizational survival (Mayhew in Ali & Ahmed, 2017).

Employee Commitment

It is necessary for every organization to have full level of its employee commitment in order to have outstanding commitment on long term basis Mowday, Porter, & Steers (2022). Increase in commitment level of employees in organization ultimately increases the commitment of their employees. In the past,

organizations use to provide job security to their employees to improve their commitment level in the organization and to improve their productivity (Abelson, 2021). Higher level of employee commitment in the organization for individual projects or to the business is assumed as a major reason for better employee commitment that leads to organizational success. Employee commitment can also be increased when the employees are more satisfied with their job and duties as well. Their satisfaction may depend on the rewards system, the organizational culture and employee knowledge sharing (Mowday et al., 2022) Meyer, Stanley and Parfyonova (2022) define commitment using a multidimensional approach and consider it to have affective, continuance and normative perspectives. The affective dimension of commitment refers to an emotional attachment to and involvement with an organization; continuance commitment denotes the perceived costs of leaving an organization; and normative commitment refers to the felt responsibility to support and remain a member of an organization. Thus it can be discerned from definitions such as the one above, that employee commitment is a bond between the employee and the organization such that he/ she (the employee) wants to continue serving the organization and to help it achieve its objectives. Yilmaz and Çokluk-Bökeoğlu (2008) expound that employees with high organizational commitment feelings affect organizational commitment in positive ways because they lessen the frequency of performing negative behaviour and improve quality of service. A committed employee is a more compatible and productive individual who has higher levels of satisfaction, loyalty and responsibility. They continue to observe that organizational commitment not only increases the success in a certain role, but also encourages the individual to achieve many voluntary actions necessary for organizational life and high standard system success.

Park, Christie and Sype (2021) advance that committed employees may be more likely to engage in organizational citizenship behaviours that is, extra-role behaviours, such as creativity or innovation which are often what keep organizations competitive. Creativity according to Bosiok and Sad (2023) is the ability to think in ways and forms that are new, different and not seen in other individuals.

Affective commitment: Affective commitment refers to the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization. Employees with a strong affective commitment continue employment with the organization because they *want to*. According to Mowday (2022), the antecedents of affective commitment generally fall into four categories: personal characteristics, structural characteristics (organizational), job-related characteristics, and work experiences. Affective commitment refers to the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization. Employees with a strong affective commitment continue employment with the organization because they want to. According to Mowday (2022), the antecedents of affective commitment generally fall into four categories: personal characteristics, structural characteristics (organizational), job-related characteristics, and work experiences.

Continuance commitment: Continuance commitment refers to an awareness of the costs associated with leaving the organization. The potential costs of leaving an organization include the threat of wasting the time and effort spent acquiring nontransferable skills, losing attractive benefits, giving up seniority-based privileges, or having to uproot family and disrupt personal relationships. Apart from the costs involved in leaving the organization, continuance commitment will also develop as a function of a lack of alternative employment opportunities. Employees whose primary link to the organization is based on continuance commitment remain because they need to. Continuance commitment refers to an awareness of the costs associated with leaving the organization. The potential costs of leaving an organization include the threat of wasting the time and effort spent acquiring nontransferable skills, losing attractive benefits, giving up seniority-based privileges, or having to uproot family and disrupt personal relationships. Apart from the costs involved in leaving the organization, continuance commitment will also develop as a function of a lack of alternative employment opportunities. Employees whose primary link to the organization is based on continuance commitment remain because they need to.

Normative Commitment: Normative commitment reflects a feeling of obligation to continue employment. Employees with a high level of normative commitment feel that they ought to remain with the organization. Wiener (organization) suggests that the feeling of obligation to remain with an

organization may result from the internalization of normative pressures exerted on an individual prior to entry into the organization (family or cultural orientation), or following entry (organizational orientation). However, normative commitment may also develop when an organization provides the employee with “rewards in advance” (paying collegetuition), or incurs significant costs in providing employment (eg head-hunting fees or the costs associated with job training). Recognition of these investments causes employees to feel an obligation to reciprocate by committing themselves to the organization until the debt has been repaid (Scholl, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

This study is suitably anchored on Equity Theory propounded by Adams (1965). This is because most empirical studies have relied heavily on these theories as the baseline theory when discussing organizational justice and workers citizenship behaviour (Greenberg, 1997; Rishipal & Manish, 2018; Antoncic and Antoncic, 2021, and Adams, 1965). According to Adams (1965), equity theory focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational partners. It proposes that individuals who perceive themselves as either under-rewarded or over-rewarded will experience distress, and that this distress could lead to efforts to restore equity within the relational cycle. It focuses on determining whether the distribution of resources is fair to both relational parties. Equity is measured by comparing the amount of contributions and benefits of each person within the relationship. Partners do not have to receive equal benefits or make equal contributions, as long as the ratio between these benefits and contributions is similar. Equity theory acknowledges that subtle and variable individual factors affect each person’s assessment and perception of their relationship with their relational partners (Adams, 1965). In any case, an employee wants to feel that his contributions and work commitment are being rewarded with his pay. If an employee feels underpaid then it will result in the employee feeling hostile towards the organization and perhaps his co-workers, which may result in the employee not performing well at work anymore. It is the subtle variables that also play an important role in the feeling of equity. Just the idea of recognition for the job commitment and the mere act of thanking the employee will cause a feeling of satisfaction and therefore help the employee feel worthwhile and have better outcomes. Adams (1965) proposes assumptions of equity theory as follows: Individuals seek to maximize their outcomes; groups can maximize collective rewards by developing accepted systems for equitably apportioning rewards and costs among members; when individuals find themselves participating in inequitable relationships, they become distressed and individuals who perceive that they are in an inequitable relationship attempt to eliminate their distress by restoring equity. The greater the inequity, the more distress people feel and the more they try to restore equity. Equity theory has been widely applied to business settings by industrial psychologists to describe the relationship between an employee's motivation and his or her perception of equitable or inequitable treatment. In a business setting, the relevant dyadic relationship is that between employee and employer. Equity theory in business, however, introduces the concept of social comparison, whereby employees evaluate their own input/output ratios based on their comparison with the input/outcome ratios of other employees (Poole, 2007). Inputs in this context include the employee time, expertise, qualifications, experience, intangible personal qualities such as drive and ambition, and interpersonal skills. Outcomes include monetary compensation, perquisites, benefits, and flexible work arrangements.

The theory was related to the study because of the set of variables formed into propositions, or hypotheses that specify the relationship among variables, typically in terms of magnitude or direction (Creswell, 2017). A theory explains how and why the variables are related, thereby acting as a bridge between the variables. The key theories on organizational justice and organizational directed organizational justice that are relevant to the study variables are reviewed in this theory. The concepts of organizational justice are today being supported, developed, and understood using a variety of theoretical frameworks and models of equity theory (Greenberg, 2007).

Bashabsheh (2018) examined the impact of distributive justice on crystallization of organizational similarity in Jordanian public institutions: a field study. This study aimed to identify impact of the

distributive justice on the organizational similarity in Jordanian public institutions. To achieve objective of the study, a questionnaire was prepared to collect data and to be distributed to the sample members. a sample consisted of (919) items was selected and the statistical package (SPSS) was used to carry out the statistical analysis for this study. Standards of descriptive statistics, simple regression analysis, multiple regression analysis, Pearson Correlation, and regression coefficient were used in this study. The study concluded a set of results: The employees' perceptions of the distributive justice dimensions were average. The procedural justice dimension was ranked first while the distributive justice was ranked last. The employees' perceptions of level of the organizational similarity were high. The organizational similarity dimension was ranked first while the organizational loyalty dimension was ranked last. There was statistically significant effect for the distributive justice dimensions in the organizational similarity.

Qatawneh (2018) examined the impacts of distributive justice on the organizational loyalty. This study aimed at identifying impacts of the distributive justice on the organizational loyalty of the employees working at the administrative departments of (Karak, Tafila, and Maan) governorates. The study population consisted of all (2444) employees working in the administrative departments of the said governorates. A simple random sample consisted of (700) an employee was selected where the questionnaires were distributed to the study members. The study concluded the following results: There is a strong and important correlation between the distributive justice and the organizational loyalty. There is a statistically significant effect for the distributive justice dimensions in the organizational loyalty. There are statistically significant differences between the respondents' conceptions about the distributive justice attributed to the demographic variables (experience, salary, and age).

Akanbi and Ofoegbu (2018) examined the role of distributive justice on organizational commitment in a multinational organization in Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the significant difference between procedural justice and perceived organizational commitment, and also to examine the significant relationship between distributive justice and perceived organizational commitment. The study results indicated that distributive justice as measured by procedural justice and distributive justice can have a significant impact on the organizational commitment of employees.

Kalay, (2021) examined the Impact of Distributive justice on Employee Commitment in Turkey. The study was conducted based on data collected from 942 teachers working in public schools in three Turkish metropolitan cities. The hypotheses were tested using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) techniques. The findings of the study indicated that among the three aspects of distributive justice, distributive justice has a positive and significant impact on task commitment. However, it was determined that the other two aspects, procedural justice and interactional justice, have no significant impact on task commitment.

Wang, Liao, Xia and Chang, (2010) examined the impact of distributive justice on work commitment in China. The study developed and tested a model that identifies the impact of distributive justice on work commitment. The model examined the mediating role played by organizational commitment and leader-member exchange (LMX) in linking organizational justice and work commitment. The data were collected from 793 completed questionnaires sampling employees from industries across the People's Republic of China. The questionnaire included scales to measure distributive justice, organizational commitment, LMX, and work commitment. The measurement of constructs and the hypothesized relationships among variables were assessed by the use of structural equation modeling. The Baron and Kenny approach was used to test the mediating effects. The findings revealed that the relationship of organizational justice to work commitment was mostly indirect, mediated by organizational commitment and LMX. Also, among the three kinds of distributive justice, interactional justice was the best predictor of commitment. Lastly, organizational commitment accounted for more of the variance than LMX did in the mediating mechanism.

Omobola (2022) investigated the influence of distributive justice on the organizational commitment of library personnel in public universities in South-West Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted. A total remuneration was used. Findings showed that distributive justice had a significant influence on

organizational commitment of library personnel. The findings also revealed that distributive justice and interactional justice significantly influenced the affective commitment of library personnel while procedural justice was not significant. Furthermore, distributive justice and interactional justice had a significant influence on the continuance commitment of library personnel while procedural justice had no significant effect on the continuance commitment of library personnel. The study concluded that distributive justice increased organizational commitment of library personnel in public universities. The study would serve as a contribution towards solving the challenges of lack of organizational commitment in academic libraries. It was recommended that library management should involve the personnel in their decision-making processes.

Fasakin (2021) examined the impact of distributive justice on employee commitment using Guinness Nigeria Limited. A total of 200 respondents were selected from the staff of the organization using convenience sampling techniques. Descriptive statistics, Pearson product moment correlation and regression analysis were employed in analyzing the data retrieved from the respondent. Findings reveals that procedural justice, distributive justice, informational justice and interactional justice all predicted employee commitment with (. Also, positive and significant relationship exists between procedural justice, distributive justice, informational justice and interactional justice and employee commitment. The study recommended that management should be fair in justice so as to ensure that there is no preferential treatment to employees. This no doubt will ensure that employee put in all their best in workplace and help achieve the organizational goal.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. Descriptive survey research design was considered appropriate because it enables the researcher to carefully, describe and explain factual and detailed information about the variables under study. Nworgu (2021) asserted that descriptive survey design is one in which a group of people are studied by collecting data through questionnaire or interview. This design is suitable for this study because it enable the researcher to elicit opinions and facts from respondents for the test of hypotheses. This study was carried out in Delta states. The sources of data for this research were primary and secondary data. The primary data for the study was collected through the distribution of the copies of questionnaire. Primary data are first-hand information specially collected for the study. Secondary data consist of information from internet, textbooks, Journal and hand books of the oil and gas firms. The study population for this research comprised 600 staff from two oil and gas firms operating in Delta State Nigeria. All permanent senior of Exxon Mobil Nigeria Corporation and Nigeria Agip Oil Company were studied. The sample size for the study was consist of the entire population (600) due to the manageable size of the population. To ascertain the validity of the instrument, the instrument was subject to content validity by giving it to three experts to validate. While test re-test method was carried out to achieve reliability. The analysis of data was performed using SPSS package. This involved simple percentage analysis to answer research questions. Simple regression analysis was used to assess the effect of Distributive Justice on employee commitment. P value was considered significant at level 0.05. Data were cleaned before analysis to ensure that they were correctly captured from source documents.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Questionnaire Distribution Analysis

A total of six hundred copies of questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, out of which five hundred and fifty were properly filled and found relevant to the study. This shows a response rate of 97.2 percent. 16 copies of questionnaire were invalid with the rate of 2.8 percent. Therefore, the analysis in this section was based on the five hundred and fifty relevant copies. The first section of this chapter covers the demographic features of the respondents while the second section analyzed the data relevant to research questions.

Presentation of Data relevant to the Research Questions

Research Question One: *To what degree does equity in pay level distributive justice affect employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Respondents view on the effect of equity in pay level distributive justice on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies

	Frequency	Percent
Agree	251	46
Strongly Agree	190	35
Neutral	60	11
Disagree	30	5
Strongly Disagree	19	3
Total	550	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024/SPSS

Table 1 reveals that greater percentage 46% of respondents agree that equity in pay level distributive justice affect employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies, 35% strongly agree, 11% are neutral, 5% disagree while 3% of respondents strongly disagree.

Research Question Two: *To what level does equal recognition distributive justice on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Respondents opinion on the effect of equal recognition distributive justice on affective commitment in oil and gas companies

	Frequency	Percent
Agree	210	38
Strongly Agree	200	36
Neutral	75	14
Disagree	51	9
Strongly Disagree	14	3
Total	550	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024/SPSS

Table 2 shows that greater percentage 38% of respondents agree that equal recognition distributive justice on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, 36% strongly agree, 14% are neutral, 9% disagree while 3% of respondents strongly disagree.

Research Question Three: *How does rewards distributive justice affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State,, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Respondents opinion on the effect of distributive justice affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies

	Frequency	Percent
Agree	210	38
Strongly Agree	200	36
Neutral	75	14
Disagree	51	9
Strongly Disagree	14	3
Total	550	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024/SPSS

Table 3 shows that greater percentages 38% of respondents agree that rewards distributive justice affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, 36 % strongly agree, 14 % are neutral, 9 % disagree while 3% of respondents strongly disagree.

4.4.1 Hypothesis One

Ho: Equity in pay level distributive justice has no significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria

Hi: Equity in pay level distributive justice has a significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Continuance Commitment	-.696	.052		-13.324	.000
Equity In Pay Level Distributive Justice	.976	.017	.935	56.187	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Continuance Commitment

The Equity in pay level distributive justice had a Beta coefficient of 0.935 indicates a positive significance between equity in pay level distributive justice and employee continuance commitment, which is statistically significant (with $t = 56.187$, $p = .000$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Thus Equity in pay level distributive justice has a significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Equal recognition justice has no significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Hi: Equal recognition justice has a significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Affective Commitment	.674	.080		8.416	.000
Equal Recognition Justice	.753	.044	.627	17.220	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Affective Commitment

The Equal recognition justice had a Beta coefficient of 0.627 indicates a positive significance between Equal recognition justice and affective commitment, which is statistically significant (with $t = 17.220$, $p = .000$). Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Thus Equal recognition justice has a significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Rewards distributive justice has no significant effect on affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

Hi: Rewards distributive justice has no significant effect on affect normative commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria

		Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Normative Commitment	-.447	.031		14.324	.000
	Rewards Distributive Justice	.411	.022	.287	18.561	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Normative Commitment

Rewards distributive justice had a Beta coefficient of .287 indicates a positive significance between Rewards distributive justice and Normative Commitment, which is statistically significant (with $t = 18.561$; $p = .000$). But Rewards distributive justice which is not statistically. Therefore, the null hypothesis should be rejected and the alternative hypothesis accordingly accepted. Thus rewards distributive justice has a significant positive effect on normative commitment in oil and gas firms in Delta State,, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

This work evaluated the effect of organizational justice on employee commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, The data generated were analyzed and the following were evident.

1. Equity in pay level distributive justice has a significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies in Delta State, Nigeria
2. Equal recognition justice has a significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies in South-South, Nigeria
3. Rewards distributive justice has a significant positive effect on normative commitment in oil and gas firms in Delta State,, Nigeria

CONCLUSION

This work evaluated the distributive justice and organizational commitment in oil and gas company in Delta State, Nigeria. Distributive justice as presented above and its impact on employee commitment in the organization is a very important and contemporary subject of interest amongst management scholars. Distributive justice which is generally regarded as the first dimension of organizational justice is about the perception of an employee. From the findings, it was discovered that equity in pay level distributive justice has a significant effect on employee continuance commitment in oil and gas companies; equal recognition justice has a significant effect on affective commitment in oil and gas companies and rewards distributive justice has a significant positive effect on normative commitment in oil and gas firms in Delta State,, Nigeria . Therefore, the study concluded that distributive justice had a significant positive effect on employee commitment oil and gas companies in Delta State,, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the outcome of the study from the findings, it in glaring that there is always justice in organization which have effect the commitment of employee. Emanating from this the study recommended that:

1. Management oil and gas firms should adopt equity in pay level distributive justice to enhance employee commitment and transparent structure that ensures equitable compensation for employees based on their qualifications, experience, and responsibilities eliminate perceptions of unfairness and promote employee commitment within organization.
2. Management of oil and gas firms should provide equal recognition justice through ample professional development opportunities for staff, including training programs, workshops, and conferences to enhance their skills and knowledge, leading to improved job commitment,
3. Based on the result of the study, we highly recommend that owners and managers of organisations should give adequate attention to rewards distributive justice within the organization as a means of

improving the commitment of employees in the workplace. so as to instigate a positive employee work behaviour.

REFERENCES

- Abdul, S., Muqqadas, R. & Sumaira R. (2018). Distributive justice and employee contextual commitment: the moderating effect of organizational respect. *Pakistan Business Review*. 3,(4),995-1010
- Aboagye, E. S. (2021). Dimensions of Distributive justice which best predict employee trust and productivity in Ghanaian higher education institutions. A *Thesis* To The Department Of Organization And Human Resource Management, University Of Ghana Business School, University Of Ghana, Legon
- Abubakar, M. A. & Salisu U.(2017). The impact of organizational support and justice on employees job satisfaction in Kano State Polytechnic. *JORIND* 15,(2) 194-103
- Adams, J. (1965). Inequity in social exchange, in Berkowitz,L.(Ed), *Advances in Experiential Social Psychology*, Vol.2. *New York Acedamic Press*, pp. 267-299.
- Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequity in social Exchange. In Berkowitz, L. (ED), *Advance in Experimental Social Psychology*, Academic Press, New York, Middle Atlantic state of the United States.
- Addai, P., Kyeremeh, E., Abdulai, W. & Sarfo, J.O. (2018) Distributive justice and job satisfaction as predictors of turnover intentions among teachers in the Offinso South District of Ghana.*European Journal of Contemporary*. 7(2), 235-243
- Adikaram, D.S.R. (2021). Impact of employee commitment on employee job satisfaction in private sector commercial banks of Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Innovative Technology*. 3 (11)18-33
- Adnan, A. A. & Qadar, B. B. (2018). The Effect of Distributive justice on Job Satisfaction: A Comparative Study of Public and Private Universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa
- Ahmad, M. B., Wasay, E., & Malik, S. U. (2022). Impact of Employee Motivation on Customer Satisfaction: Study of Airline Industry in Pakistan, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(6), 531-539.
- Ahmed, M. D. (2021). Relationship between employee commitment and employee commitment and engagement At Nairobi City County government. A Research *project* for the award of degree of Master of Science in Human Resource Management, School of Business, University of Nairobi
- Ahmed, W., Muhammad Y., Rashed, N & Akhtar N. (2021). Employee commitment between trust and employees' commitment: A Case of Private Sector Hospitals of Hazara Division, Pakistan. *Journal of Business and Management*. 18, (9), 153-161
- Ahuja, K. 2006. *Personnel management*. 3rd Ed. New Delhi. India. Kalyani publishers,
- Ajala, E. M. (2021). The influence of Distributive justice on employees' commitment in manufacturing firms in Oyo State, Nigeria: Implications For Industrial Social Work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 5(1), 92
- Ajala, E.M. (2015) The influence of organisational justice on employees' commitment in manufacturing firms in Oyo State, Nigeria: Implications for industrial social work. *African Journal of Social Work*, 5(1), 93-130.
- Akanbi, P.A & Ofoegbu, O.E. (2013). Impact of perceived organisational justice on organisational commitment of a food and beverage firm in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(14), 207-218.
- Ali, N. & Jan, S. (2012). Relationship between organisational justice and organisational commitment and turnover intentions amongst medical representatives of pharmaceutical companies of Pakistan. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, 6(2), 201-212.
- Allen N.J, Meyer J.P (2011), A three component conceptualization of organizational commitment, *Human. Res. Manage. Rev.*, 1:61-89.

- Alsalem, M. & Alhaiani, A. (2007). Relationship between organizational justice and employee performance. *Journal of Industrial Relations and Organizational Behaviour*, 5(3), 97-110.
- Amah, E. (2021). Distributive justice and employees' commitment to supervisor in selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 2321–8916).
- Cagliyan, V., Attar, M. & Derra, M. (2017). The relationship between organizational justice perception and organizational commitment: A study on Dogus Otomoyive Authorized Dealers in Kenya. *Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 22(2), 599-612.
- Celik M, & Sariturk M. (2022). Distributive justice and motivation relationship; The case of Adiyaman University. *Istanbul Ticoret Universiti Sosya Bilimler Degisi* 11(21): 353–382.
- Chan , A. (2022). Employees Commitment and its impact on Organizational Performance. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 5(2), 1-13.
- Chima L. (2019). Motivation and Job Satisfaction in the Nigerian Public Service : Issues ,Problems , and Challenges . *International Journal of Liberal Arts and Social Science*. 2(6): 207–214.
- Chinomona, E. & Dhurup, M. (2015). The role of organizational commitment in the organizational citizenship behaviour and employee intention to stay relationship: The case of Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Humanities and social Sciences*, 5(7), 47-58.
- Chordiya, R, Sabharwal, M, & Goodman, D. (2017). Affective organizational commitment and job satisfaction: a cross-national comparative study. *Public Administration* 95(1),178-195.
- Durrani, A. B., Cheema, S., Khokhar, M.F. & Pasha, A.T. (2015). Exploring the relationship of organizational justice with employee satisfaction and employee"s commitment. *International Journal of Science, Basic and Applied Research*, 24(6), 156-167.
- Elovainio, M., Kivimaki, M. & Vahtera, J. (2002). Organizational justice: Evidence of a new psychological predictor of health. *American Journal of Public Health*, 92(1), 105-108.
- Faruk, K. (2021). The impact of Distributive justice on employee commitment: a survey in Turkey and Turkish context. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 6(1),1-11.
- Gamage, D. (2014) "How should government promote distributive justice? A framework for analysing the optimal choice of tax instrument". Maurer Faculty, 2413.
- Ggreenberg,. J. (1987). A Taxonomy of Organizational Justice Theories," *Academy of Management Review*, vol. 12,(1). 9–22,
- Gichira, P. M. (2021).Influence of Distributive justice on commitment of employees in health sector non-governmental organizations in Kenya . A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment for the Award of the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Human Resource Management in the Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.
- Gim, C., & Desa, N. (2014). The impact of distributive justice, procedural justice, and affective commitment on turnover intention among public and private sector employees in Malaysia. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanity*, 4(6).
- Guha, A.B. & Chimote, N.K. (2012). Organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behaviour and work life balance. *India Journal of Commerce and Management Studies*, 3(1), 57-62.
- Hassan, A. (2002). Organizational justice as a determinant of organizational commitment and intention to leave. *Asian Academic & Management Journal*, 7(2), 55-66.
- Harif, A.R., Dara, Y.R. & Hendra, L. (2021). Distributive justice, job satisfaction and organizational commitment as antecedents of employee commitment: a study in Indonesia National Health Insurance Workers. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, volume 100.
- Herman, S. & Armanu, A. (2013). Organizational justice, organizational commitment and trust in manager as predictor of organizational citizenship behaviour. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 133(4), 12
- Karanja, G.W. (2021) Effect of Distributive justice on organizational commitment in public secondary schools and commercial banks in Kenya. A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in Human Resource Management in the Jomokenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.

- Khaleh, L.A.B.C. & Naji, S. (2016). The relationship between organisational commitment components and organisational citizenship behaviour in nursing staff. *Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 39-45.
- Komendat, N. & Didona, T. (2021) . Employee commitment and employee’s perception of job security. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 6, (1), 3-28
- Mahmut. D. (2011), Effects of organizational justice, trust and commitment on employees’ deviant behavior”, *An International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research* Vol. 22 (2), 204–221
- Meyer, J. P., & Parfyonova, N. M. (2020). Normative commitment in the workplace: A theoretical analysis and re-conceptualization. *Human Resource Management Review*. 5 (2), 10-22
- Meyer, J.P. & Allen, N.J. (2021) A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human resource management review*, 1; 1(1),61-89.
- Mitchell, J. I., Gagne, M., Beaudry, A. & Linda, D. (2022). The role of perceived organizational support, distributive justice and motivation in reactions to new information technology. *Computer in Human Behaviour*, 28, 729 – 738.
- Moazzezi, M., Sattari, S. & Bablan, A.Z. (2019). Relationship between Distributive justice and job commitment of Payamenoor University employees in Ardabil Province. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies*, 2(6).
- Moon, K. (2017). Fairness at the organizational level : Examining the effect of Distributive justice climate on collective turnover rates and organizational commitment. *Public Personnel Management* 1(2), 1–26.
- Moosa, M., Sadraddin, S. & Adel, Z. B. (2019). Relationship between Distributive justice and job commitment of payamenoor University employees in Ardabil province. *Singaporean Journal Of Business Economics, And Management Studies*.2, (6), 67-78
- Noman, S., Demirel A.S., (2023). Impact of employee commitment on organizational performance. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* 1(3)
- Nuruzzaman, T. & Talukder H K. (2021). Original Article Distributive justice and Employees Service Behavior in the Healthcare Organizations in Bangladesh : An Agenda for Research. *Bangladesh Journal of Bloet hics*; 6(3), 10–24.
- Nyaribo, L. O. & Dennis J. (2017). Effect of employee commitment on Employee Commitment a Case of Urban Roads Authority. *International Journal of Science and Research*.6 (6),70-96
- Ogwuche, C.H., Musa, M.H. & Nyam, J. (2018). Influence of perceived Distributive justice and organizational climate on job commitment among secondary school teachers in Makurdi metropolis. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 86(2), 278–321.
- Ohana, M. (2019). A multilevel study of the relationship between Distributive justice and affective commitment: The moderating role of organizational size and tenure. *Personnel Review*, 654-671.
- Orishede, F. & Bello, A. (2019). Relationship between Distributive justice and employees’ commitment. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 7(1), 2019.
- Osman, H., Ibuathu, C. N.&Rukangu, S.(2021). Influence of employee commitment on employee job satisfaction: A case of Northern Rangelands trust in Isiolo County, Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*. IV, 11,443-457
- Özer, O., Uğurluoğlu, O& Meltem, S. (2017). Effect of Distributive justice on work engagement in healthcare sector of Turkey. *Journal of Health Management* 19(1), , 62–70
- Paracha, A.T., Azeem, M., Malik, S. & Yasmin, R. (2017). Impact of Distributive justice on employee commitment: mediating role of emotional intelligence: an analysis of Public Sector Organizations in Pakistan. *Global Development in Humanities, Education and Civilization* (GDHEC 2017).
- Rahman, A. Shahzad, N., Mustafa, K., Khan, M.F. & Qurashi, F. (2016). Effects of organizational justice on organizational commitment. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(3), 188-196.

- Rathore, M. & Sen, C. (2017). Organizational justice and organizational commitment: A study on it sector. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(4), 117-124.
- Ren, T. & Hamann, D. (2021). Employee commitment and job attitudes: the role of occupational status, *Personnel Review*. 44 4, 550-566
- Saadati, M., Saadati, A., Asghari A., Bidgoli, M.G, & Bidgoli, A.G. (2021). The relationship between perceived Distributive justice , organizational commitment and job satisfaction. *Health, Sprituality and Medical Ethics*; 3(1), 10–17.
- Sharp, M. A., (2021). Gaining employee commitment: Linking to Organizational effectiveness. *Journal of Management Research*, 5(1): 250-268
- Syarifah H. B. A. (2021). The impact of Distributive justice on employee intrinsic and extrinsic commitment: A Case Study In Kota Kinabalu Polytechnic, Malaysia. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review..* 5, (11),
- Timinepere, C. O., Agbaeze, E. K., Ogbo, A. & Nwadukwe, U. C.(2018). Distributive justice and Turnover Intention among Medical and Non-Medical Workers in University Teaching Hospitals. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*
- Vijaya M. (2021).Analyzing the impact of employee commitment on labor turnover. *Great Lakes Herald*. 10, (1), 70-81
- Visagie, C. M., & Steyn, C. (2021). Organizational commitment and responses to planned organizational change: An exploratory study. *Southern African Business Review*, 15(3), 98-121.